

Resolution of Some Methanols containing Pyridyl Group

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Tertiary carbinols as *n*-octylphenyl 2-pyridyl and *n*-octylphenyl 4-pyridyl methanols have been prepared by the interaction of 2 and 4 benzoyl pyridine with appropriate Grignard's complex and resolved by the classical method.

Tertiary carbinols of the type $R.R'R''$. C. OH where R is phenyl, R' is 2 & 4 pyridyl and R'' is methyl, ethyl, *n*- and iso-propyl, butyl and amyl groups have been prepared by previous workers^{1,2,3}. In search of antihistaminic agents it was thought to prepare some more tertiary carbinols having R'' as *n*-octyl, such as *n*-octyl phenyl 2-pyridyl and *n*-octyl phenyl 4-pyridyl methanols by the interaction of 2 & 4 benzoyl pyridine with appropriate Grignard Complex. The resolution was achieved with the use of optically active acids like *d*-tartaric acid and *d*-camphor 10-sulphonic acid to get (+) *n* octyl phenyl α -pyridyl methanol [α]_D³⁵ + 3.96 (1, 1 : c, 2.5 in ethanol) and *n*-octyl phenyl γ -pyridyl methanol [α]_D³⁵ + 4.2 (1, 1 : c, 3.8 in ethanol). The optical rotation in different solvents have also been recorded.

Some secondary carbinols like methyl α -pyridyl and methyl β -pyridyl carbinol have been prepared by Tschitschibabin and Meerwin Ponderof Verely reduction methods^{4,5}, and resolutions attempted.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of ($\pm$) Methyl 2-pyridyl carbinol from 2-acetyl pyridine: In Tschitschibabin's method of reduction, sodium (18 g.) in absolute alcohol (200-225 ml) and zinc dust (30 g.) were treated with 2-acetyl pyridine (18 g.) and refluxed. The carbinol so obtained was crystallised from benzene-light petroleum in plates, m.p. 39-40°; yield 46%. Found: N, 11.85%, C₇H₉NO required: N, 11.39%.

Attempts to resolve the above carbinol: Attempts to prepare crystalline salts of this ($\pm$) carbinol with optically active acids like (+) tartaric acid, (+) camphor-10-sulphonic acid, and (+) camphoric acid were unsuccessful.

Preparation of ($\pm$) methyl 3-pyridyl carbinol from 3-acetyl pyridine: In Meerwin Ponderof Verely reduction method, dry isopropyl alcohol (300 ml), aluminium iso-propoxide (120 g.) and 3-acetyl pyridine (30 g.) were refluxed and ($\pm$) carbinol was obtained, b.p. 106-107°/5-7 mm; yield 38%. Found: N, 12.01%, C₇H₉NO requires: N, 11.39%.

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2. J. Kenyon and K. Thaker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 659.
3. U. S. Pathak and K. Thaker, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **41**, 555.
4. A. E. Tschitschibabin, *Ber.*, 1904, **37**, 1370.
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Attempts to prepare crystalline salts of this carbinol with the same optically active acids were not successful.

Preparation of ($\pm$) n-octyl phenyl α -pyridyl methanol: The Grignard complex was prepared in dry ether from n-octyl bromide (38.6 g; 0.2M) and magnesium turnings (4.8 g.). Ether from Grignard complex was evaporated and the Grignard reagent was taken up in dry benzene (75 ml). To the cooled mixture phenyl α -pyridyl ketone (18.3 g; 0.1 M) in benzene (100 ml) was added during stirring and the contents heated under reflux for 2 hr. and allowed to keep overnight at room temperature. On decomposition, the ethereal layer was washed, dried (sodium sulphate) and evaporated. The residue on keeping in refrigerator for several days gave crystalline solid carbinol, brown plates from petroleum ether, m.p. 38-40°; yield 39%. Found N, 4.19%, $C_{20}H_{27}NO$ required N, 4.71.

(+) *n-octylphenyl α -pyridyl methanol:* d-Camphor-10-sulphonic acid (6.96 g.) was added to a solution of ($\pm$) above carbinol (8.76 g.) in warm ethanol (42 ml), the less soluble camphor-10-sulphate (crop A) (10.4 g) was decomposed by sodium carbonate (5.2 %) to get partially active (+) carbinol (5.82 g) [α]_D³⁵ + 1.02 (1, 1: c, 2.3 in ethanol). The carbinol after two similar crystallisations from ethanol gave (+) carbinol (1.75 g), m.p. 38°, [α]_D³⁵ + 3.96 (1.1: c, 3.22 in ethanol) which did not increase on further crystallisations.

(+ 1.94	c, 3.55 in ethyl acetate)
(+ 2.30	c, 2.29 in acetone)
(+ 2.46	c, 5.21 in benzene)
(+ 2.52	c, 4.64 in chloroform)
(+ 3.50	c, 4.57 in methanol)

(—) *n-octyl phenyl α -pyridyl methanol:* The more soluble camphor-10-sulphonate in the filtrate from crop A was concentrated, cooled and decomposed (sodium carbonate 5.2%). The (—) carbinol was extracted with ether (25 ml) and ether layer washed, dried (sodium sulphate) and evaporated to get (—) carbinol m.p. 39°. [α]_D³⁵ — 2.64 (1, 1: c, 3.4 in ethanol).

Preparation of ($\pm$) n-octyl phenyl γ -pyridyl methanol.

($\pm$) n-octyl phenyl γ -pyridine methanol was prepared as above from n-octyl bromide (38.6 g; 0.2 M), magnesium (4.8 g; 0.2 M) and phenyl γ -pyridyl ketone (18.3 g; 0.1 M) in dry ether (100 cc) and dry benzene (100 c.c.). The carbinol was crystallised from petroleum ether, m.p. 118-120°, yield 42%. Found N, 4.13%, $C_{20}H_{27}NO$ required N, 4.71%.

(+) *n-octyl phenyl γ -pyridyl methanol:* ($\pm$) n-octyl phenyl γ -pyridyl methanol (8.7 g.) in ethanol (45 cc) and d-tartaric acid (4.5 g.) gave crop A—the less soluble (+) hydrogen tartrate (9.2 g.), m.p. 147-148°, [α]_D³⁵ + 0.82 (c, 3.2 in ethanol). Crop B, m.p. 152-153°, [α]_D³⁵ + 1.72 (c, 1.2 in ethanol) gave crop C & D with further increase in optical rotation. Crop D then gave crop E (2.8 g.) which gave (+) carbinol (1.12 g.) which did not increase in optical rotation on further crystallisation, [α]_D³⁵ + 4.2 (c, 5.8 in ethanol) m.p. 114°.

(+ 1.20	c, 4.21 in chloroform)
(+ 1.57	c, 6.52 in toluene)
(+ 2.24	c, 3.01 in acetone)
(+ 3.59	c, 2.26 in benzene)
(+ 3.80	c, 2.87 in methanol)

(—) *n*-octyl phenyl γ -pyridyl methanol: The filtrate containing more soluble hydrogen tartrate was concentrated on water bath. Then it was decomposed with sodium carbonate (5.2 %), extracted with ether, washed and dried (sodium sulphate) and evaporated to get (—) carbinol (2.42 g.), m.p. 113-114°, $[\alpha]_D^{35} -3.50$ (1,1: c, 6.73 in ethanol).

Preparation of ($\pm$) ethyl methyl 3-pyridyl carbinol: This was prepared from magnesium (4.8 g. ; 0.2 M), ethyl iodide (31.4 g. ; 0.2 M) in dry ether (100 cc) and 3-acetyl pyridine (12.0 g. ; 0.1 M) in ether (100 cc), b.p. 114-116°/5-7 mm. Found N, 4.23%, $C_9H_{13}NO$ required N, 4.64%.

Attempts to prepare crystalline salts of the above ($\pm$) carbinol with optically active acids like (+) tartaric acid and (+) camphor-10- sulphonic acid were unsuccessful.

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